

Technology Transfer in Vietnam Security Area

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Abstract:

The article conducts an overview of research related to science and technology transfer in the field of security industry. The author conducted a review on many aspects such as the content of science and technology transfer, review on the results of previous studies, review of research methods used in previous studies, Review of the theory used. Finally, the author proposes research gaps and future research directions in Vietnam's security sector, particularly at the General Department of Logistics, Ministry of Public Security, Vietnam.

Keywords: Technology transfer, security, police, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In response to the requirements of the country's renovation and development, in the current international economic integration context, the scientific capacity and potential of our country and the Ministry of Public Security have been constantly improved. The technology content in many products has increased the quality and added value for goods and services, helping to improve the competitiveness of units inside and outside the police. The scientific staff is better equipped with research facilities and equipment through investment programs of the State and the Ministry of Public Security. The system of science and technology organizations is supported and facilitated to transform the management structure to suit the specific situation of each unit. Technology market has been gradually formed, promoting technology application and transfer activities, promoting commercialization of scientific research results, linking scientific research results with practical activities of the industry. Security.

In order to meet the increasing demands of the country's industrialization and modernization in the new stage, effectively using investment resources for science and technology, science and technology should be developed. in the direction of considering the development and application of technology transfer results as the top national policy, one of the most important drivers for socio-economic development, national defense and maintaining political security. safety and order of society.

According to functional regulations and tasks of units in the General Department of Logistics and Engineering of the Ministry of Public Security, a number of specialized technical equipment must be mass produced domestically and the concept of "industrial security. Security »was set up and considered as a key industry, it has an important role in the sustainable development of national security protection in the current situation.

However, our security industry is facing ever greater opportunities and challenges. In general, the current system of research and production facilities of the security industry is small in scale, not commensurate with the requirements of the police for combat and force building in the new stage. The products of means, professional techniques, specialized weapons, support tools to equip units and localities are still lacking in quantity and of low quality; material foundations, equipment and technological levels of most research and production establishments have a low high technology content. Currently, the technical equipment of the security industry can only meet 50% - 60% of the demand

The question is how to have a strong security industry for sustainable development to meet the increasingly demanding needs of the cause of national security protection. Many technology transfer deals from abroad to Vietnam are aimed at serving the operations of police forces, ensuring national socio-economic security. However, in these deals, most of the Vietnamese side did not have access to the countries that own the source technology, resulting in limited ability to absorb and develop technological capacity from the technology transferred from the country. health.

2. Foreign research situation

2.1. Studies on the implications of technology transfer

In foreign countries, the concept of technology transfer is known for a long time, and technology transfer is considered as one of the leading spearheads for economic development. There have been many in-depth studies on technology transfer in many countries.

When it comes to technology transfer, most of the authors around the world deal with the concepts of technology and technology transfer and related issues. Each author approaches these terms from different perspectives. Tyhanyi and Roath (2002), Mascus (2003) consider technology as information, so technology transfer is the transfer of information from sender to receiver.

Hawthome (1971), Galbraith (1972), Pacey (1983) and Goulet (1989), Levin (1996), Reisman (2006) consider technology as the application of science, tools and knowledge to solve a problem. Thus, technology transfer is defined as an application of new technology for new use or for new users (Rodrigues, 1985).

Many other authors consider technology as a process (Woolgar, 1987; Methe, 1991) or a "structural ring" (OECD, 1992). From the above points of view, technology transfer theories have developed definitions of technology transfer, which refer to technology transfer as a process by which an organization adopts an innovation. done by another organization (Roger, 1962), or a learning process (Shiowattana, 1987), a socio-engineering process that implies the transfer of cultural skills with the movement of machinery, equipment and tools (Levin, 1993); the process by which ideas and theories move from laboratory to market (Phillips, 2002); Any process by which one party can access another party's technical information and successfully learn and absorb it into production (Mascus, 2003).

In this angle, the AUTHOR synthesizes and absorbs the previous authors' research to determine the concept as well as the scope of the technology, serving his research purposes.

Regarding international technology transfer (ITT): Since ITT is involved in politics, economics, commerce, culture, technology, law and so on, each researcher has studied ITT from a different perspective. together. Although 50 years have passed now, the theory of ITT has not yet formed a complete and independent system (Xu, 2007). Most research focuses on foreign direct investment, joint ventures, transfer patterns and economic development. Existing research lacks an integrated relationship between different theories. Some ITT theories are unilateral and distributed (Xu, 2007).

AUTHOR selectively absorbs previous studies to serve their research purposes.

Regarding technology transfer approaches, many authors stand on the perspective of technology transfer recipients (Li.Q, 2014; Sanjay Kumar et al, 2015; Astrid Szogs, 2010; Rashid Ali Al-Saadi, 2010), but there are also a number of works in the position of technology transferors for research (Bozeman, 1994; Geisler and Clements, 1995; Sandelin, 1994; Phillip H. Phan and Donald S. Siegel, 2004) . In addition, many studies in the perspective of international technology transfer (Xu, 2007; Li.Q, 2014;), while others focus on analysis of internal technology transfer. or domestically, transferring knowledge from laboratories or schools to enterprises (Carayannis, Rogers, Kurihara & Allbritton, 1998; Steffensen, Rogers & Speakman, 1998; Everett M. Rogers, Jing Yin, Joern Hoffmann , 2000).

2.2. Studies on technology transfer model

There are a number of foreign scholars who approach from the perspective of qualitative modeling, and from there build some models, such as the Behrman and Wallender Model (1976) which proposes a seven-stage process in national technology transfer. international relations involving multinational corporations; Dahlman and Westphal (1981) with a 9-stage model with a focus on transfer participation at all phases of the technology transfer project. Models by Schlie, Radnor, and Wad: Schlie et al. (1987) proposes a simple general model, outlining seven factors that can influence the planning, implementation, and eventual success of any technology transfer project. Chantramonklasri (1990) proposes a five-stage model suitable for technology transfer in major countries such as China and India. Each model has its own application, and also has its own advantages and disadvantages. However, the common feature of these models is that there is no specific quantitative assessment to know the impact of these factors on the success / efficiency of technology transfer.

When considering the purpose of technology transfer: many studies evaluate the results of technology transfer and the factors that influence (Li.Q, 2014; Sanjay Kumar et al, 2015; Astrid Szogs, 2010; Rashid Ali Al

-Saadi, 2010)., While other studies focus on technological capacity or technological innovation (Tang Ming Feng, 2009; Jean-francois Eck, 2011), ability to absorb technology (Reddy and Zhao, 1990); Cohen and Levinthen, 1990; Gibson and Smilor, 1991; Keller, 2004; Gopalakrishnan and Santoro, 2004; Santoro and Bierly, 2006; Arvanitis and Woerter, 2009; Kneller et al., 2010).

AUTHOR relies on the models of Schlie et al and the analysis of some other authors such as Li.Q to build his research model on the basis of quantitative analysis to determine the factors affecting results of technology transfer in the field of security industry, from which appropriate solutions are offered.

The above studies either only evaluate in terms of effectiveness, or evaluate the effects on effectiveness.

2.3. Research on technology transfer in the field of security industry

Regarding the security industry, there is not much research on this new industry, some prominent authors in this area include ASIS Foundation, 2013; Vincent Boulanin, 2012; Ecorys research and Consulting, 2009; Martí Sempere, C., 2010. However, these studies are often either from the perspective of the defense industry, or from the perspective of the general security industry (including military and civilian). that includes security in the armed forces and private security at companies that provide security services).

In his research, the AUTHOR only approached from the perspective of the security industry in the armed forces, (specifically at the General Department of Logistics and Engineering under the Ministry of Public Security), not in the corner. military degree (defense) or at private security service firms. This is also a new topic and has not been studied by many authors, so this can also be considered as a new point in the study.

Regarding technology transfer in the security industry, there is currently no research on this issue. However, only a few works by other authors have focused on the defense industry, not on the security industry perspective (James B. Rose, BS, 1995), or There are studies to mention the impact of technology transfer on national security as research by Wayne M. Johnson (1998). These studies either do not mention public civil security (of the armed forces), or only general mention of technology transfer to the economy as a whole, of which a small part on national security, not to mention the efficiency of technology transfer in the security industry. These are the gaps in the research that the AUTHOR could exploit.

2.4. About the research method

Many researches on technology transfer use qualitative research methods, but some authors have used quantitative models to evaluate technology transfer activities such as Li.Q (2014), Rashid Ali Al-Saadi (2010) or use research systems analysis (AHP) methods such as Sanjay Kumar et al. (2015) or empirical analysis methods such as Ana Carina Araújo and Aurora A.C. Teixeira (2013).

AUTHOR relies on quantitative modeling studies to evaluate the efficiency and impact of these factors on the efficiency of technology transfer.

In short, the issue of technology transfer in the Vietnamese environment in general and technology transfer to the armed forces in particular has not been mentioned by any foreign research. No topic has mentioned fully, systematically and deeply about technology transfer activities as well as the efficiency of technology transfer in the security industry in Vietnam in general and in the Department of Logistics - Engineering, Ministry of Public Security in particular.

3. Research situation in Vietnam

The National Assembly passed the Law on Technology Transfer from 2006, until 2017, enacted the Law on New Technology Transfer, but the issue of technology transfer in the security industry is still quite vague with many people.

3.1. Research on technology transfer

There are quite a lot of researches on this field in Vietnam, authors or groups of authors through their research works, such as books, textbooks, thesis (Ho Sy Hung, 1996), Journal articles have clearly shown the theoretical basis of technology transfer (Department of Technology Management, 2013), as well as experimental studies in certain fields (Pham Duc Nghiem et al, 2011), summarizing the experience of technology transfer in the world for Vietnam (Dang Kim Nhung, 1994; Shoichi Yamashita; Luu Quy Tan translation, 1994) or the status of technology transfer in Vietnam (Phan Xuan Dung, 2004) either in the management areas (Ngo Van Que, 2001), or related to international investment projects (Ha Thi Ngoc Oanh,

2006).

Many books and textbooks on technology transfer also contribute to enriching content related to technology transfer such as Technology Transfer Curriculum by Vu Chi Loc (2016), Technology Monographs and technology transfer by Phan Xuan Dung (2017).

However, in general, these studies often mention in general about technology transfer in Vietnam, there is no topic about technology transfer in a particular industry such as security industry. However, the theoretical issues and research results of the above authors will be selectively selected by the AUTHOR to include in their research.

3.2. Research on technology transfer model

There are very few researches on technology transfer models in the field of security industry in Vietnam. In the process of researching this topic, the author himself has a few related reports, including an article on the model of factors affecting technology transfer in the field of security industry. 2018 and research on the efficiency of technology transfer in the security industry (2018), which identifies the factors that make up the efficiency of technology transfer.

3.3. Security industry studies and technology transfer in the security industry

In the field of security industry, legal documents of Vietnam, as well as the Ministry of Public Security also repeatedly mentioned this term, but still have no clear definition, lack of standards and regulations. to be specific about this new industry.

Regarding this content, almost no research in the country mentioned, except for some documents of management agencies such as Ministry of Public Security, General Department of Logistics and Engineering. In which, the project "Promote the development of defense and security industries to meet the requirements of building and defending the country in the new situation", was passed in the Resolution of the XII Congress of the Party; Resolution 06, Notice of Conclusion 25 / TB-TW, dated 11-4-2017 of the Politburo (Session XII) and the Project "Development of Security Industry" approved by the Prime Minister in 2015 are text refers to the security industry.

In addition, there are several individual studies on security and security industry by many authors, gathered and published by the Theoretical Council of Vietnam Ministry of Public Security in 2014 and some studies by Tran. Dai Quang, Nguyen Quang Yem (2015) have raised some issues about security industry products and the definition of security industry. However, theories about technology transfer in the security industry are mostly lacking, the author has not found any research that mentions a systematic and comprehensive technology transfer in the security industry. security.

Currently, there are only a few studies on technology transfer in the security industry, but most of them are done only in terms of analysis of the defense industry. The page cacnuoc.vn has also made a few points about military technology transfer in the context of globalization.

3.4. About the research method

Most research on domestic technology transfer uses qualitative methods. There have also been a number of research papers by domestic authors using quantitative research methods, mainly identifying factors affecting technology transfer promotion (Nguyen Thi Van Anh, 2015). or in transfers from research institutions to businesses, not to mention transfers in the security industry sector.

AUTHOR has synthesized and referenced research methods that are currently used in the field of technology transfer and used survey methods to obtain primary data to clarify the operational factors. technology transfer, thereby serving as the basis for analysis, proposals and solutions to promote technology transfer in the security industry.

In short, in the past few years, there has been a lot of technology transfer activities in the security industry, but there is still no insight into the theoretical and practical issues of the transfer. technology in this area. There is still a lack of in-depth scientific and research topics in the field of technology transfer, especially technology transfer in the armed forces, contributing to socio-economic development and ensuring security and order in the situation. new present. The problem of how to really transfer technology effectively, in order to promote the development of a new, nascent industry like security industry? This question needs to be studied seriously.

Through the review of research projects in Vietnam, it can be seen that there is no research topic on technology transfer in the security industry in Vietnam and at the General Department of Logistics - Engineering (Ministry Police). These are also gaps that the AUTHOR can take advantage of to do his research.

4. Conclusion and future research orientation

In the above studies, the author found some gaps in the research, which can be listed as follows:

4.1. About the research content

There are not many studies in the world on the security industry, mainly on the defense industry. In Vietnam today, the concept of security industry is vague, and is often understood within the scope of the defense industry. Therefore, there are no studies on security industry in Vietnam, moreover at the General Department of Logistics and Engineering.

Although there are many researches on technology transfer in the world and in Vietnam, in many different angles, research on technology transfer in the security industry is also quite rare in the world. , and mainly approached from the perspective of the defense industry, or private security due to the confidentiality of this topic. In Vietnam, the author has not seen any research on this topic. These are content gaps for future research.

4.2. About the research method

Research projects in the world use a lot of qualitative, quantitative methods or a combination of both, research works in Vietnam mainly use qualitative methods. Future studies absorb and selectively use quantitative research methods in analyzing the factors affecting technology transfer in specific fields such as the security industry, thereby providing solutions. Appropriate measures aimed at improving efficiency in this activity, ensuring the development of the security industry in the coming years.

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